

Factors Affecting The Application Of Sustainable Accounting And Sustainable Development In Enterprises

Nguyen Phu Giang, Tran Nguyen Bich Hien, Nguyen Thi Ha

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: July 24, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: February 26, 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Sustainable Accounting (SA), Sustainable Accounting Framework, Traditional Financial Accounting</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6296441</p>	<p><i>The article synthesizes macro and micro perspectives on sustainability accounting on the views of objectives, measurement methods, principles, and sustainability accounting reports. The article also analyzed that applying sustainability accounting can lead to enhanced sustainable development in enterprises. Research also shows that the application of sustainability accounting will bring the sustainable development of both businesses and society, promoting businesses to adopt sustainability accounting voluntarily. The article also identifies and measures the factors affecting the application of sustainability accounting in enterprises.</i></p> <p><i>One hundred ninety-seven manufacturing enterprises in 6 sectors are surveyed: fertilizer production, steel production, rubber processing, plastic packaging production, and food processing. The primary data analysis method was used for this study is the SEM structural equation modeling method. The article used AMOS software to evaluate and measure the influence of each factor on the application of sustainable accounting in enterprises.</i></p> <p><i>We have also successfully demonstrated that if implemented, sustainable accounting will bring the sustainable development of both business and society.</i></p>

Introduction

The role of accountants in sustainable development is actively discussed in academic literature. Gray, R. (1994) points to the need for a critical approach to understanding the role of accounting and business in sustainable development. Moldan, B., Billharz, S., et al. (1997) provides a critical review of sustainable development initiatives in the accounting profession and proves the necessity for a more pragmatic approach to achieve accounting impact on sustainable development. According to Lambertson, G. (2000), 8 from 17 targets directly related to accounting. Accountants can influence their achievement and, at the same time, transforming accounting according to the new challenges from sustainable corporate development. There have been many types of research on sustainability accounting, including the history and role of sustainability accounting; however, there have been no studies on developing from traditional accounting to sustainable accounting.

This paper investigates how to develop a sustainable accounting framework based on the structure of the financial accounting model. This study aims to provide direction for the future development of sustainability accounting at both the conceptual and applied levels.

From the synthesis of previous studies, we build and design a sustainable accounting framework developed from traditional financial accounting based on the following contents:

- The goal of sustainable accounting
- Fundamentals of sustainability accounting
- Measurement techniques and data collection in sustainability accounting
- Sustainability accounting report format
- Attributes of sustainability accounting
- Factors affecting the application of sustainable accounting and the sustainability of enterprises

2. Litterature

According to Rubenstein, D. B. (1994), most of the different approaches to sustainability accounting are based on traditional accounting principles. Westing, A. H. (2016) describes an accounting model that includes conventional financial statements (profit and loss statements and balance sheets), generally accepted accounting principles that underlie the preparation of financial statements. According to Ijiri (1983), the traditional accounting system consists of accounting records and accounting reports as the main accounting tools. The basis for the preparation of traditional financial statements are accounting records prepared using tools such as journal entries, ledgers, and trial balances, and most importantly, the double-entry principle. According to Ijiri, the design of these tools is directly linked to the performance appraisal function of

accountants. In sustainability accounting, the accountant's goal is sustainability. Using a deductive approach (Martin, 2014), a sustainability accounting model can be designed to provide information that allows the assessment of results towards achieving the firm's sustainability goals. Thus, sustainability accounting must also be approached based on elements of financial accounting (traditional accounting): Accounting reports (Elliot & Jacobson, 1991); Accounting principles (DeeSAN, C., & Newson, M., 2017); Accounting documents (Ijiri, 1983); Objectives of the accounting model (Martin, 2014); Qualitative Attributes (SAC 3).

Environmental accounting research, which part of sustainability accounting has focused considerable attention on the value of assets, liabilities, and environmental costs, using generally accepted accounting principles. Milne (1991) considers a variety of estimation techniques to serve in the valuation of environmental assets. Still, sustainability accounting is more inclined to provide the social and environmental impacts of corporate activities.

Product lifecycle analysis presents an enormous challenge in sustainability accounting due to the complexity of detailed measurement of environmental impacts. The life cycle analysis method is carried out from when raw materials enter the business until the product is consumed and used. Environmental data can be collected using general scientific models to estimate emissions and resource consumption. In the case of resources purchased from a supplier, it is possible to measure directly with technical equipment. Assume that water meters can be used to record consumption...

In many cases, sampling is the most cost-effective data collection method due to its cost. The cost of measuring all emissions and natural resources is too much. Primary records forming part of the sustainable accounting system could include, for example, a pollution inventory and a resource consumption inventory. Like the sub-records maintained in the conventional accounting system, these inventories are used to record the data from which the final statements are extracted.

3. Theoretical framework

To design an accounting system, it is indispensable to determine the accounting principles to be applied the tools used to record, measure, and analyze. The last step of an accounting system is to provide information, so accounting reports are needed. In addition, accountants need to comply with several attributes that are considered accounting requirements, such as timeliness, accuracy, punctuality, objectivity.

Objective of sustainability accounting framework	Principle understanding sustainability accounting framework	Data capture recording and measurement techniques	Reporting	Qualitative attributes of sustainability accounting information
Measure performance of organization toward goal of sustainability Discharge accountability to stakeholders Provide decision-useful information	Reporting entity Definition of sustainability Accounting period Scope Materiality Capital maintenance Units of measurement Precautionary principle	Performance indicators Valuation Life-cycle analysis Primary data capture Primary records	Reporting formats Reporting frequency	Transparency Completeness Accuracy Timeliness Auditability Relevance Comparability Clarity Neutrality Sustainability context Inclusiveness

Figure 1 – The sustainability accounting Framework

Objectives of the sustainability accounting framework

The main objective of the sustainability accounting framework is to measure performance towards sustainability. At the heart of this is the debate over whether sustainability is an appropriate goal at the organizational level and whether it is measurable. There have been many studies on sustainability, but they are all from a macro perspective. On a micro view, such as within an enterprise or organization, there are very few studies. The concept of sustainable development is widely accepted as a multi-level concept (Jones, M. J., 2003) in which the levels are highly interdependent. Modern research towards global

sustainability requires action at all levels. Rules have been devised to achieve maintainability at the macro level, but the translation of these rules to the micro level is an unresolved issue.

As with conventional accounting information, potential internal users of sustainability accounting information need to be distinguished from external users. Businesses need to determine when providing sustainability information externally means accepting accountability for their environmental and social impacts to a range of external stakeholders. Sustainability accounting information should represent transparency and comparability in the relevant sustainability context. This allows stakeholders to assess an organization's environmental and social impact and contribute to its sustainability goals. Making sustainable accounting information available to internal users will focus on helpful decision-making by management. For example, a range of performance metrics and lifecycle data against the associated sustainability goals will assist the organization's internal control towards multidimensional sustainability.

The main objective of the sustainability accounting framework is to measure the performance of an organization towards its sustainability goals. Performance measurement information for sustainability can serve useful purposes of accountability or decision clarity in providing conventional accounting information (Ijiri, 1983). Crucial to this goal is the chosen definition of sustainability, which determines the depth and complexity of the accounting framework. Enterprises need to identify the selected sustainability criteria economically (for example, annual revenue growth of at least 10%), socially (create jobs for at least 2,000 employees, one-year doing charity at least 50,000 USD...), in terms of environment (annual cost for environmental conservation is at least 30,000 USD, the yearly cost for waste treatment is at least 50,000 USD...)

Sustainability metrics

The most common approach to measuring sustainability in business is often chosen as the three-dimensional concept of economy, society, and environment. Measuring performance against a multidimensional view of sustainability requires a range of social, environmental, and economic indicators. Which issue should be prioritized will lead to different levels of sustainability accounting information. A compromise then is to develop composite performance indicators that measure two or more aspects of sustainability, such as ecological performance indicators.

Sustainability at the enterprisescale to measure the impact of the business on the natural environment, the boundaries of the sustainability accounting system need to be clearly defined to limit the scope of activities. Manageable. We can imagine: Primary environmental impact refers to the direct impacts of the unit on the environment. Second-degree environmental impact is the impact caused by input suppliers. Third-level impacts are incidental to the provision of inputs. In previous studies, the boundary was drawn to include first and second-degree environmental impacts, but not to mention third-degree impacts (Bebbington, J., & Gray, R., 2001).

In our opinion, to measure the sustainable development of enterprises, it is possible to use the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI). GRI uses a range of metrics to measure performance towards sustainability goals. GRI is a long-term, multi-stakeholder international process tasked with developing and disseminating globally applicable Sustainability Reporting Guidelines. This guide is used voluntarily by organizations to report on the economic, environmental, and social aspects of their activities, products, and services (GRI, 2002).

The use of indicators to estimate variables that cannot be measured precisely has been used for a long time in environmental science (Moldan et al., 1997). The GRI indicators are considered appropriate when using complex variables that are not directly observable. The latest version of the GRI, released at the World Summit on Sustainable Development (WSSD) in Johannesburg in August 2002, provides a rigorous framework for adopting sustainability reporting.

Table 1 -GRI framework for performance indicators

	Category	Aspect
Economic	Direct economic impacts	Customers Suppliers Employees Providers of capital Public sector

Environment	Environmental	Materials, energy, water Biodiversity Emissions, effluents, waste Suppliers Products and services Compliance transport Overall
Social	Labour practices and decent work	Employment Labour/management relations Health and safety Training and education Diversity and opportunity
	Human rights	Strategy and management Non-discrimination Freedom of association and collective bargaining Child labour Forced and compulsory labour Disciplinary practices Security practices Indigenous rights
	Society	Community Bribery and corruption Political contributions Competition and pricing
	Product responsibility	Customer health and safety Products and services Advertising Respect for privacy

Source: GRI, 2002, p. 36.

Sustainable accounting principles

The sustainability accounting principles are similar to the principles and conventions that underpin financial accounting, such as cost, going concern, and prudential regulations and those relating to the accounting period and reporting units.

Gray, R. (1993) proposes to use capital maintenance accounting principles applied to sustainability accounting in the natural capital inventory and sustainability cost accounting approaches. The definition of sustainable development in the direction of inherent preservation implies the maintenance of ecological, social, and economic capital. It leads to the controversial issue of substitutability between natural materials and renewable materials (Costanza & Daly, 1992).

The principle of materiality is also consistent with the sustainability accounting framework. Due to the interconnectedness inherent in the natural environment, capturing and reporting all anthropogenic environmental impacts is not feasible. Impacts should be prioritized depending on their importance as a potential threat to the human species or the natural environment and their relevance to stakeholders. Lesser threats will not affect users of the information and can be excluded from materiality-based sustainability reports.

The principle of materiality should be considered together with ecological prudence so that action to reduce environmental impacts is not delayed due to scientific uncertainty (CICA, 2014). Consequences that may not be precisely measurable or where the risk is low may still require reporting to the information users. An example is a high risk but low probability (Rubenstein, 1994), which should be considered regarding the potential impact on information users due to their potential to be ecologically, socially, and economically destructive.

Measure

To fully reflect social and environmental factors in the concept of sustainability requires using a wide range of units of measurement. A monetary unit is suitable for measuring economic performance, but not for measuring social or environmental performance; attempting to measure social and ecological impacts in financial terms risks distorting and underestimating the importance of these issues relative to economic matters.

Tools for collecting and recording accounting data

The data management tools used to collect and record sustainability accounting data are similar to financial accounting's diaries, ledgers, and balance sheets (additional openings are required, books for detailed tracking against selected sustainability goals). Measurement techniques include using performance indicators and valuation methods used to estimate, for example, environmental assets and liabilities... Use additional metrics to measure against selected sustainability criteria.

Sustainability information report

Once sustainability metrics have been identified and measured, they need to be reported to provide information. Therefore, the reporting period for sustainability data should be defined. Other than Financial Statements, different sustainability reports can be generated monthly, quarterly, and annually, e.g., updating web pages (maybe several times per day) with the latest information and product and service lifecycle reports. The use of life cycle analysis is considered crucial to the sustainability accounting process as it contributes to the shift of planners' timing from the short-term accounting period to the long-term product life cycle (Broadhead, L., 2002).

Data collected by the sustainability accounting framework will be reported to users as quantitative and qualitative information. They should match a range of attributes as listed in Table 1, drawn from the GRI Guidelines, and are equivalent to the attributes specified in the required accounting system.

The format of sustainability reports used to present sustainability accounting information includes:

- Actual value indicators measure performance during an accounting period (CICA, 2014).
- Natural capital inventories are segregated into different categories (Jones, 1996).
- Estimate the cost of sustainable alternatives to existing business (Gray, R., 2002).
- Input-output analysis (Jasch, 1993).
- Life cycle analysis.
- List of cases of non-compliance with relevant laws
- Describe and report on environmental and social impacts.

Some common types of sustainability accounting information are using websites when available, rather than following a fixed reporting schedule. This motivates users to check websites regularly for updates.

Attributes of sustainable accounting

The fifth component of the sustainability accounting framework defining the qualitative attributes of sustainability accounting information has been drawn from the GRI Guidelines. Attributes should be woven together into a cohesive framework. These attributes are called reporting principles (refer to Figure 2 taken from page 23 of the GRI Guidelines)

Figure 2- Attributes of sustainability accounting

Source: GRI, 2002, p. 23.

These attributes, drawn primarily from financial accounting, are designed to inform users of how reports have been prepared (GRI, 2002, p. 22). The key attributes are: Transparency requires disclosure of all processes, procedures, and assumptions during report preparation (GRI, 2002, p. 24); Comprehensiveness requires reporting enterprises to provide information to stakeholders in a systematic way to help focus and continuously improve the quality of their reports (GRI, 2002, p. 24); Auditability requires that the data and information provided be recorded, compiled, analyzed, and disclosed in a manner that allows internal or independent auditors to attest to the reliability of the audit (GRI, 2002, p. 25). The remaining qualitative attributes are designed to ensure the quality, reliability, and accessibility of reported information relevant to the organization's sustainability goals. Sustainability accounting information must have these qualitative attributes to enable report makers to exercise their accountability to users (SAC 3, 2002, p. 23).

4. Factors affecting the application of sustainable accounting in enterprises

4.1. Research sample

We surveyed 197 enterprises via online questionnaires to identify and measure the factors affecting the application of SA in Vietnam by using AMOS data analysis software. We have analyzed 197 listed companies: 27.9% is fertilizer, 21.3% is steel manufacturing, 16.2% is rubber processing, 11.7% is plastic packaging, and the rest is food processing.

The respondents to the survey are representatives of the board of directors in charge of finance and accounting. The survey and data collection period were from December 2020 to September 2021. This study's primary data analysis method was the structural equation modeling method (SEM) with AMOS - SPSS. To obtain a reliable estimate for this method, according to Tauchen (1986), the sample should usually be more extensive than 200 ($n > 200$). Based on the empirical rule of Hair et al. (2010), for one estimate variable, the minimum sample size needed for this study was $n > 8 \times \text{number of variables} = 8 \times 23 = 184$. Combining the above principles, the sample size, we choose with $n = 197$. The research used variable of sustainable accounting that measured by legal regulator system related to SA, level of competition of enterprises in the same field, a strategy of the business, enterprise accounting system (Turner, P. and Tschirhart, J. (2017), Leung Pah Hang, M.Y., Martinez-Hernandez (2016), Ekins, P., 2019). At the same time, the article also proved that the application of SA affected the sustainability of enterprises.

Our research hypothesis is:

H1: The legal regulatory system affects the application SA

H2: The level of competition of enterprises in the same field affect the application of SA

H3: The strategy of business affects the application SA

- H4: The enterprise accounting system affects the application SA
 H5: The characteristics of enterprises affect the application of SA
 H6: The legal regulatory system affects the level of sustainability of the business
 H7: The characteristics of the supply chain affect the level of sustainability of a business
 H8: The strategy of company involves the level of sustainability of a business
 H9: The enterprise accounting system affects the level of sustainability of a business
 H10: The characteristics of enterprises affect the level of sustainability of a business
 H11: The application of SA affects the level of sustainability of a business

4.2. Factors affecting the application of SA and the level of sustainability of a business

Table 3 - KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.	.874
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square
	2838.532
	Df
	276
	Sig.
	.000

After running the rotation matrix, the coefficient $KMO = 0.874 > 0.5$, $sig = 0.000 < 0.05$, so the model is satisfactory, there are seven groups of factors that converge and have cumulative loadings at $66.47\% > 50\%$, which showed that the independent variables explained 66.47% of the dependent variable.

Table 4 - Pattern Matrix

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
CP2	.863						
CP1	.826						
CP4	.800						
CP3	.774						
AC4		.923					
AC3		.796					
AC1		.756					
AC2		.714					
CH2			.863				
CH1			.776				
CH3			.634				
CH4			.562				
SA3				.852			
SA2				.849			
SA1				.795			
LR2					.843		
LR1					.807		
LR3					.705		
LS2						.858	
LS3						.822	
LS1						.699	
ST1							.935
ST3							.717
ST2							.619

Extraction Method: Principal Axis Factoring.

Rotation Method: Promax with Kaiser Normalization.

a. Rotation converged in 7 iterations.

Pattern Matrix rotation matrix is used to analyze factor confirmatory in AMOS software, to see whether the factors are convergent and discriminant.

Table 5 - Regression Weights: (Group number 1 - Default model)

		Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Label
SA <---	CP	.332	.089	3.729	***	
SA <---	AC	.038	.008	-.435	.004	
SA <---	CH	-.105	.119	-.884	.377	
SA <---	ST	.218	.089	2.456	.014	
SA <---	LR	.434	.104	4.185	***	
LS <---	CH	<u>.240</u>	.122	-1.966	.049	
LS <---	LR	-.033	.111	-.302	.763	
LS <---	ST	-.011	.091	-.119	.905	
LS <---	CP	.214	.095	2.247	.025	
LS <---	AC	.354	.092	3.837	***	
LS <---	SA	.367	.098	3.767	***	

Using the 95% confidence standard, the sig of CH affecting SA is $0.377 > 0.05$, and the variable CH has no effect on SA; sig of LR affecting LS is $0.763 > 0.05$ and sig of variable ST affecting LS is $0.905 > 0.05$, so LR, ST has no effect on LS. The remaining variables all have sig equal to 0.000 or < 0.05 (AMOS sign *** is equal to 0.000), so these relationships are significant. Thus, 4 variables are affecting SA, including CP, AC, ST, LR; 4 variables are affecting the LS, including CH, CP, AC, SA. Of the 11 hypotheses, we reject H5, H6, H8 and accept the remaining hypotheses. (Table 5)

Table 6 - Standardized Regression Weights

	Estimate
SA <--- CP	.334
SA <--- AC	.040
SA <--- CH	-.093
SA <--- ST	.225
SA <--- LR	.385
LS <--- CH	.222
LS <--- LR	-.031
LS <--- ST	-.012
LS <--- CP	.223
LS <--- AC	.381
LS <--- SA	.382

Continue to consider the Standardized Regression Weights table, and this is the normalized regression coefficients table. We will rely on the Estimate regression coefficient in this table to evaluate the impact of the independent variables on the dependent variable. Among the four variables that affect SA, the order of decreasing variables is as follows: LR (0.385), CP (0.334), ST (0.225), AC (0.04). Among the 4 variables affecting LS, the order of decreasing effect: SA (0.382), AC (0.381), CP (0.223), CH (0.222) (Table 6).

Table 7- Squared Multiple Correlations

Variables	R2	Variables	R2
SA	.628	LR1	.650
LS	.707	LR2	.780
ST2	.452	SA1	.714
ST3	.587	SA2	.653
ST1	.750	SA3	.477
LS1	.604	CH4	.486
LS3	.670	CH3	.582
LS2	.615	CH1	.630
LR3	.683	CH2	.676
LR1	.650	AC2	.694
LR2	.780	AC1	.570
SA1	.714	AC3	.733
SA2	.653	AC4	.719
SA3	.477	CP3	.664
LS2	.615	CP4	.685
LR3	.683	CP1	.739

Finally, we consider the Squared Multiple Correlations table. This table shows the R-squared value of the impact of the independent variables on the dependent variable.

The R-squared value of SA is $0.628 = 62.8\%$, so the independent variables affect 62.7% of the variation of SA. Similarly, the R squared of the LS is $0.707 = 70.7\%$, so the independent variables affect 70.7% of the variability of the LS.

The summary results of the influences of factors on the application of SA and the sustainability of business are as follows:

Figure 4 – The influences of factors on the application of SA and the sustainability of the business

5. Conclusion

The article has synthesized macro and micro perspectives on sustainability accounting in terms of objectives, measurement methods, principles, and sustainability accounting reports. The article also proves that the application of sustainable accounting in enterprises is affected by competitive pressure (CP) of enterprises in the same industry, accounting system (AC), business strategy, state legislation (LR). Factors such as characteristics of the business (CH), competitive pressure of other enterprises in the same field, accounting system (AC), and finally, sustainability accounting (SA) affect the development of corporate sustainability (LS).

One crucial thing drawn from this study is that sustainability accounting will help businesses and society develop sustainably. The article also identifies and measures the factors affecting the application of sustainable accounting in enterprises, proving that the application of sustainability accounting impacts the sustainable development of enterprises.

The research results also show that if the state or government has regulations on applying sustainable accounting (for example, it is mandatory to publish some sustainable accounting indicators), it will significantly affect the application of sustainable accounting (LR with the maximum impact factor of 0.385). In addition, the competitive pressure of enterprises in the same field also has a significant impact on the application of SA (impact coefficient 0.334).

Moreover, applying sustainable accounting will have a significant impact on the sustainable development of the business (the impact coefficient of SA on LS is the highest 0.382). In addition, the enterprise's accounting system also has many influences on the application of sustainable accounting and the sustainable development of the enterprise.

A synthesis of previous studies also shows that sustainable accounting is a related issue related to the sustainable management of natural ecosystems, which are new ideas and concepts in environmental science. The main components of sustainability accounting are the problem of rational use of resources and providing measurement methods and approaches. Sustainability accounting is also an essential informational tool for decision making, leading to optimal exploitation of resources, protection, and prevention of environmental threats.

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Author Information

Prof.Dr, Nguyen Phu Giang
Thuongmai University

Dr, Tran Nguyen Bich Hien
Thuongmai University

Dr, Nguyen Thi Ha
Thuongmai University
